

The Digitalization of Distributor Management System at Pertamina Lubricants: Issues and Solutions on the Implementation Stage

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ABSTRACT: Pertamina Lubricants has stated digital transformation as one of its breakthrough projects to accelerate digitalization as one of its strategic initiatives. This strategic initiative has objectives to enhance channel management and the capability of distributors as strategic business partners to achieve their sales volume target set by the management of Pertamina Lubricants. This journal aims to evaluate and improve the digital distributor management system to help distributors of Pertamina Lubricants achieve their sales volume target.

KEYWORDS: Acceptance level, Analytical hierarchy process, Brainstorming, Digitalization, Fishbone diagram, Perceived usefulness, Perceived ease of use.

INTRODUCTION

Pertamina Lubricants has several strategic initiatives to accelerate its business performance to be a World Class Lubricants Company. One of the strategic initiatives is digitalization. Pertamina Lubricants implements a new digital system as one of the strategic priorities to support its daily business operation throughout all divisions. One of them is the Distributor Management System (DMS). This digital transformation system is developed under the sales and marketing team of PT Pertamina Lubricants to manage the operations and process of secondary sales conducted by its distributors as business partners.

However, the current conditions of DMS implementation for the distributors do not meet the expectation of Pertamina Lubricants. Those conditions resulted in Pertamina Lubricants finding it challenging to evaluate and review its distributors' secondary sales operations and activities. Pertamina Lubricants cannot precisely determine the right and effective sales and marketing promotional program to help distributors to increase their sales volume. This journal aims to evaluate and improve the digital distributor management system to help distributors of Pertamina Lubricants achieve their sales volume target.

PROBLEM STATEMENTS

The implementation of Distributor Management System (DMS) has been executed since 2021 in the hope to improve the secondary sales operation and activities of the distributors to achieve the sales volume target. But unfortunately, the acceptance level of the distributors for DMS is low.

What are the problems that make the low acceptance level of DMS for the distributors? How can PT Pertamina Lubricants formulate alternatives and choose the best solutions to push the distributors to utilize DMS entirely in their business process to achieve sales volume targets?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology that will be used in this journal is based on primary data and secondary data. Primary data are gathered from in-depth interviews of 8 (eight) distributors with the best KPI performance in the year 2021 and the management of PT Pertamina Lubricants. Furthermore, secondary data are gathered from internal information such as sales growth, market share, market growth, and external information from websites, news, and other media.

To simplify the structure of the research and explain how the variables of the study link each other, the author is designing the conceptual framework to reach the desired objectives as expressed in the figure below:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework
Source: Author’s analysis

LITERATURE REVIEW

Acceptance level analysis theory

Creating and developing a new system should consider two essential things they are usefulness and ease of use (Davis, 1989). Davis explains that these two factors will significantly affect the level of acceptance of new technology. Davis (1989) defined perceived usefulness (PU) as the degree to which a person believes using a particular system would enhance their job performance. It means whether or not someone perceives that technology to be useful for what they want to do. The parameters include Helpful and Make Job Easier, Improving Productivity and Effectiveness, and Develop Job Performance. Furthermore, Davis (1989) defined perceived ease of use (PEOU) as the degree to which a person believes using a particular system would be free from effort. If the technology is easy to use, then the barriers are conquered. No one has a positive attitude towards it if it is not easy to use and the interface is complicated. The parameters include Clear and Understandable, Flexible and Easy to Use, and Learning to Operate and Become Skilled.

Problems analysis theory

Agarwal (2016) explains that the "Fishbone Diagram" or "Ishikawa Diagrams" is one of the most commonly used approaches to categorize the root cause of a problem. It is a simple visualization tool to depict various potential causes of pain. It provides a structured way to organize and represent data meaningfully. The most commonly used categories for identifying the grounds of a problem are man, methods, materials, machines, measurements, and environments. Moreover, Agarwal (2016) defines the analysis of the "Man" category helps to identify all problems that are personally related. The study of "Methods" defines any causes that deal with the process or method to perform. The "Machines" category defines all the causes related to hardware, software, and tools. The "Materials" analysis groups any causes related to external dependencies. The review of "Measurements" is used to group the causes related to incorrect data to measure the quality or success of the product. The "Environment" study causes that related to an environment of primary problem.

Brainstorming strategy theory

Al-Mutairi (2015) explains that brainstorming is one of the essential strategies in provoking creativity and solving problems in the educational, commercial, industrial, and political fields. Brainstorming means using the brain for active problem solving, and the brainstorming session aims to develop creative solutions to problems. Brainstorming combines a relaxed, informal approach to problem-solving with lateral thinking. It encourages people to come up with thoughts and ideas that can, at first, seem a bit crazy.

Analytical hierarchy process theory

Yusriana (2022) defines Analytical Hierarchy Process as a problem-solving method that starts with a thorough definition of the problem and then organizes it into a hierarchy with several levels or stages, such as goal level, criteria, and alternatives.

FINDINGS

After doing the research and analysis, there are several interesting findings that can be discussed. In evaluating the implementation of DMS for distributors, the author looked at the acceptance level of DMS and identify the problems with the current implementation of DMS for distributors.

The acceptance level of DMS

From the analysis of in-depth interviews with the distributors, the author found that the acceptance level of distributors to utilize DMS entirely is low. It can be seen from the low level of perceived usefulness and the average level of perceived ease to use.

Problem analysis

Continuing from previous findings, the acceptance level of DMS by the distributor to fully utilize DMS is low. The distributor must face problems fully utilizing DMS in their secondary sales operation. By using Fishbone Diagram, the analysis of problems faced by the distributors to fully utilizing DMS are described below:

The analysis of Man category finds that people who are already comfortable with the old system, people who are resistant to change, and people who are already overloaded with existing tasks.

The analysis of Method category found that no reward, no dedicated support, and no periodic training for the distributors.

The analysis of Machine category finds that the distributors have problems related to lagging systems, battery consumption, and complicated UI UX.

The analysis of Materials category finds that the distributors have problems with connection problems, unstable connection, and server down.

The analysis of Measurement category finds inaccurate data between DMS and own system, different data between DMS and own system, and no integrated data between DMS and other digital tools.

The analysis of Environment category finds about complex processes, not integrated systems, and no performance dashboard.

The author found that Method category is recognized as the biggest problem for the distributors that cause their acceptance level of DMS to be low.

SOLUTIONS

After getting all the findings, it shows that there are some challenges that Pertamina Lubricants faces to improve the acceptance level of DMS. The challenges are the low acceptance level of DMS by the distributors and the problems experienced by the distributors to utilize DMS fully. Below are the proposed solutions to overcome the challenges.

Develop Perceived Usefulness

To overcome the challenge of develop perceived usefulness, Pertamina Lubricants is suggested to provide a dedicated online and offline customer support team, the routine reward for distributor staff, and set an end-to-end Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) about operating and accessing DMS.

Develop Perceived Ease of Use

In order to develop perceived ease of use, Pertamina Lubricants is recommended to improve and develop DMS that is clear, simple, and easy to understand by using familiar terms, transparent colors, and clear letters in the form of standard User Interface and User Experience (UI and UX). Moreover, Pertamina Lubricants should provide Bahasa Indonesia as a language system in all modules.

Other Improvement Steps

Moreover, there are recommended steps sequentially to improve the acceptance level as proposed by Kroll (2022) such as:

1. Inform: Provide consistent education and share information with distributors.
2. Simplify: Using a vocabulary that the distributors understand can help improve the acceptance level.
3. Visualize: Photos, videos, and infographics are beneficial in illustrating information in an easy-to-understand style.
4. Influence: Influencers can be distributors who already fully utilize DMS very well for daily sales activities. He can slowly but surely persuade other distributors to use DMS fully.
5. Demonstrate: Demonstrations and hands-on training should be integral to introducing DMS to distributors. Allowing for kinesthetic learning ensures that all learning modalities are supported with verbal, visual, and hands-on information.
6. Encourage: The fear of failure and embarrassment when learning a new skill and working with a new DMS is a reality for distributors. To keep them from being discouraged and feeling defeated when taking on this recent change, it is vital to encourage distributors and support them.

Solving the identified problems

Based on the result of problem analysis using the Fishbone Diagram that has been analyzed in the previous chapter, this study proposes several initiatives to overcome the causes of a problem from each category:

Table 1. Proposed Initiative for Each Problem (Author Analysis)

Problem Category	Initiatives
Man	Provide a reward/incentive program to give recognition to distributors who can achieve a certain acceptance level of DMS
Method	Provide regular training, reward program, and dedicated customer support
Machine	Accelerate the development of the DMS software system to fix the lagging system, unfriendly UI-UX, battery consuming
Material	Change the GSM card with a much better coverage operator, and improve the server quality to be more stable.
Measurement	Create an integrated system (API) that can connect DMS with other digital tools and periodically check the data suitability between DMS and the distributor's system.
Environment	Simplify the system, and provide to date automatic performance dashboard that can be accessed through both PC and smartphone

Formulating Alternative Solutions

Based on an in-depth interview and brainstorming strategy with the management of Pertamina Lubricants, three alternative solutions could be taken by Pertamina Lubricants to push distributors to utilize DMS fully:

1. Periodic Training: Training should be performed periodically to distributors to refresh knowledge, enhance skills, and share and discussion about trial and error in using DMS. Periodic training needs medium cost but is easy to implement, and the expected result is medium sales volume growth.
2. Organization Support: Pertamina Lubricants can provide supporting infrastructure periodically to help distributors fully utilize DMS. The supporting infrastructures are internet data packages dedicated supporting team to guide and monitor the learning process of DMS implementation. Organization support needs medium cost, is not easy to implement, and can result in medium improvement in sales volume.
3. Incentive Alignment: The incentives should be connected to the targets of the distributors' KPI (key performance indicator). The form of incentives could be in commercial things and targeted to owners and teams of distributors. The incentive alignment needs high cost; it is not easy to implement, yet it can result in significant sales volume growth.

Table 2. Resume of Alternative Solutions (Author Analysis)

No	Alternative Solutions	Cost	Ease to Implement	Improve Sales
1	Periodic Training	Medium	Easy	Medium Growth
2	Organization Support	Medium	Medium	Medium Growth
3	Incentive Alignment	High	Medium	Significant Growth

Determining The Best Solution

After formulating three alternative solutions, the author identifies the best alternative solution to be used as a new idea to push distributors to utilize DMS fully to improve sales by using Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) below:

1. Define the overall objective

The author wants to define the best alternative solution from three options (periodic training, organization support, and incentive alignment) to be used as a new idea to push distributors to utilize DMS to improve sales fully.

2. Define the structured hierarchy consisting of attributes and alternatives.

Figure 2. (AHP) Hierarchical Structure Chart

3. Determine the priority weights of the attributes using a pair-wise comparison matrix and its consistency ratio. To construct a pair-wise comparison matrix (n x n) for criteria concerning the objective, the author uses Saaty’s 1-9 scale of pair-wise comparison. It is used to compare each criterion with each other criterion, one by one.

Table 3. Saaty’s 1-9 Scale of Pair-wise Comparisons

Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal Importance	Two activities contribute equally to the objective
2	Weak or Slight	
3	Moderate Importance	Experience and judgment slightly favor one activity over another
4	Moderate Plus	
5	Strong Importance	Experience and judgment strongly favor one activity over another
6	Strong Plus	
7	Very Strong	An activity is favored very strongly over another
8	Very, very Strong	
9	Extreme Importance	The evidence favoring one activity over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation

4. For each comparison, the author will decide which criteria are most important and then assign a score to show how much more important it is.
5. Compute each element of the comparison matrix by its column total and calculate the priority vector by finding the row averages.
6. The weighted sum matrix is found by multiplying the pair-wise comparison matrix and priority vector (eigenvalue)
7. They divide all the weighted sum matrix elements by their respective priority vector element.
8. Compute the average of this value to obtain λ_{max}
9. Find the Consistency Index (CI) as follows:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1}$$

Where n is the matrix size.

10. Calculate the consistency ratio (CR) as follows:

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI}$$

11. Judgment consistency can be checked by taking CI's consistency ratio (CR) with the appropriate value in the table below. The CR is acceptable if it does not exceed 0.10. If it is more than 0.10, the judgment matrix is inconsistent. Judgments should be reviewed and improved to obtain a consistent matrix.

Table 4. Average Random Consistency (RI)

Size of matrix	Random consistency
1	0
2	0
3	0.58
4	0.9
5	1.12
6	1.24
7	1.32
8	1.41
9	1.45
10	1.49

By following steps 3 to 11, the author tries to figure out what is the best alternative solution from the three alternative solutions below:

1. Pair-wise comparison of each criterion to each other criterion:

Priority Weights of Attributes

	Cost	Ease to Implement	Improve Sales
Cost	1.00	0.33	0.20
Ease to Implement	3.00	1.00	0.33
Improve Sales	5.00	3.00	1.00
Total	9.00	4.33	1.53

Criterion Comparison Matrix

	Cost	Ease to Implement	Improve Sales	Total	Priority	Eigenvalue
Cost	0.111	0.077	0.130	0.318	0.106	0.955
Ease to Implement	0.333	0.231	0.217	0.781	0.260	1.129
Improve Sales	0.556	0.692	0.652	1.900	0.633	0.971
Total	1.000	1.000	1.000	3.000	1.000	3.055

→ λ_{max}

Consistency Index (CI)	0.03
Random Consistency (RI)	0.58
Consistency Ratio (CR)	0.05 → consistent

2. Pair-wise comparison of “cost” criterion:

Priority Weights of Attributes

	High	Medium	Low
High	1.00	0.50	0.14
Medium	2.00	1.00	0.50
Low	7.00	2.00	1.00
Total	10.00	3.50	1.64

Criterion Comparison Matrix

	High	Medium	Low	Total	Priority	Eigenvalue
High	0.100	0.143	0.087	0.330	0.110	1.099
Medium	0.200	0.286	0.304	0.790	0.263	0.922
Low	0.700	0.571	0.609	1.880	0.627	1.030
Total	1.000	1.000	1.000	3.000	1.000	3.051

→ λ_{max}

Consistency Index (CI)	0.025
Random Consistency (RI)	0.580
Consistency Ratio (CR)	0.044

→ consistent

3. Pair-wise comparison of “ease of implement” criterion:

Priority Weights of Attributes

	Hard	Medium	Easy
Hard	1.00	0.67	0.50
Medium	1.50	1.00	0.50
Easy	2.00	2.00	1.00
Total	4.50	3.67	2.00

Criterion Comparison Matrix

	Hard	Medium	Easy	Total	Priority	Eigenvalue
Hard	0.222	0.182	0.250	0.654	0.218	0.981
Medium	0.333	0.273	0.250	0.856	0.285	1.046
Easy	0.444	0.545	0.500	1.490	0.497	0.993
Total	1.000	1.000	1.000	3.000	1.000	3.021

→ λ_{max}

Consistency Index (CI)	0.010
Random Consistency (RI)	0.580
Consistency Ratio (CR)	0.018

→ consistent

4. Pair-wise comparison of “improve sales” criterion:

Priority Weights of Attributes

	Slight Growth	Medium Growth	Significant Growth
Slight Growth	1.00	0.33	0.14
Medium Growth	3.00	1.00	0.25
Significant Growth	7.00	4.00	1.00
Total	11.00	5.33	1.39

Criterion Comparison Matrix

	Slight Growth	Medium Growth	Significant Growth	Total	Priority	Eigenvalue
Slight Growth	0.091	0.063	0.103	0.256	0.085	0.939
Medium Growth	0.273	0.188	0.179	0.640	0.213	1.137
Significant Growth	0.636	0.750	0.718	2.104	0.701	0.977
Total	1.000	1.000	1.000	3.000	1.000	3.053

→ λ_{max}

Consistency Index (CI)	0.026
Random Consistency (RI)	0.580
Consistency Ratio (CR)	0.046

→ consistent

5. Resume the value of the Priority Vector of each criterion from point a – d above (yellow column).

Criterion Priority Vector		Cost Priority Vector		Ease to Implement Priority Vector		Improve Sales Priority Vector	
Cost	0.106	High	0.110	Hard	0.218	Slight Growth	0.085
Ease to Implement	0.260	Medium	0.263	Medium	0.285	Average Growth	0.213
Improve Sales	0.633	Low	0.627	Easy	0.497	Significant Growth	0.701

6. Determine the Ranking of Alternative Solutions by multiplying the value of each criterion priority vector with the value of the priority vector of each alternative solution. For example: the cost of "Periodic Training" is medium, so the calculation is $0.106 \times 0.263 = 0.028$

Alternative Solutions				Final Rank					
	Cost	Ease to Implement	Improve Sales		Cost	Ease to Implement	Improve Sales	Total	Ranking
Periodic Training	Medium	Easy	Medium Growth	Periodic Training	0.028	0.129	0.135	0.292	2
Organization Support	Medium	Medium	Medium Growth	Organization Support	0.028	0.074	0.135	0.237	3
Incentive Alignment	High	Medium	Significant Growth	Incentive Alignment	0.012	0.074	0.444	0.530	1

After the author finishes executing the AHP analysis of alternative solutions, it can be concluded that Incentive Alignment is the best alternative solution since it has the highest total score of 0.530. The second one is Periodic Training with a score of 0.292, and the last one is Organization Support with a score of 0.237.

Based on the AHP analysis above, the author continues to conduct an in-depth interview with the management of Pertamina Lubricants to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of Incentive Alignment. The analysis uses a brainstorming strategy since this method can allow people to think more freely and out of the box.

Table 5. Advantages and Disadvantages of Proposed Best Solution (Author Analysis)

Advantages	Disadvantages
Potentially achieve significant growth of sales volume and sales revenue	Need lots of budgets to provide a reward to those distributors who achieve the target of KPI
Distributors will try to learn DMS by themselves to get rewards or incentives from this program	This solution is very dependent on other factors that can lead to the success of improving sales volume, such as sustainability of product in the supply chain process. If these factors cannot be adequately managed, there could be some backfire received by Pertamina Lubricants
The implementation of this alternative solution is not that difficult since Pertamina Lubricants has great POWER to manage distributors	Though the implementation is not that difficult, the bureaucracy and administration process still need time to make sure the implementation of this alternative comply with the rule of Pertamina Lubricants

CONCLUSIONS

The author finds there are some insights that can be considered as the conclusions from the findings and solutions that have been explained above:

1. The perceived usefulness of DMS is low. All distributors say that DMS cannot improve productivity and effectiveness. Moreover, although all distributors inform that DMS is helpful, makes the job more accessible, and develops job performance, they will not use it if it is not a compulsory system from Pertamina Lubricants.
2. The perceived ease of use of DMS is average since distributors feel it is not good enough to replace their system and still needs many improvements and developments.
3. Since the level of perceived usefulness is low and the perceived ease of use of DMS is average, it can be concluded that the acceptance level of DMS for distributors is low.
4. The problems of distributors to fully utilize DMS related to man (people) are their people already comfortable with their old system, their people who are resistant to change, and people who are already overloaded with existing tasks.
5. The problems of distributors to fully utilize DMS related to methods (process) are no reward, no dedicated support, and no periodic training held by Pertamina Lubricants.

6. The problems of distributors to fully utilize DMS related to machines (system) are lagging system of DMS, battery consumption, and complicated User Interface and User Experience.
7. The problems of distributors to fully utilize DMS related to materials (external dependencies) are connection problems, unstable connection, and server down.
8. The problems of distributors fully utilizing DMS related to measurements are incorrect data between DMS and their system, different data between DMS and their system, and no integrated data between DMS and other digital tools.
9. The problems of distributors to fully utilize DMS related to environments are the complex process of DMS, no integrated system, and no performance dashboard.
10. Among those problem factors, distributors conclude that problem related to methods is the biggest problem that causes their acceptance level of DMS to be low.
11. There are three alternative solutions to push distributors to utilize DMS entirely: periodic training, organization support, and incentive alignment.
12. Incentive alignment is the best alternative solution for Pertamina Lubricants to push distributors to utilize DMS because it can significantly improve sales growth.

EXECUTION PLAN

The author proposes a short-term implementation plan for the rest of 2022, so the plan can be executed entirely in 2023. To give a structured and practical implementation plan, the author prepares with Gantt chart as listed below in table 6

Table 6. Gantt Chart (Author Analysis)

Tasks	Sep-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	Jan - Dec 2023
Improving and Developing DMS					
Formulating Incentive Alignment to KPI					
Calculating The Budget of Incentive Alignment					
Propose The Program and Budget of Incentive Alignment to Management of Pertamina Lubricants					
Socialize Incentive Alignment Program to All Regions and Distributors					
Implement Incentive Alignment Programs for All Distributors					

With the structured agenda in the Gantt Chart, the author is optimistic that Pertamina Lubricants could get a quick win to push distributors to utilize DMS to improve sales fully. It is the perfect momentum for Pertamina Lubricants to improve and develop its DMS to be a much better digital tools for distributors. Therefore, distributors could be pushed to significantly improve their sales volume next year to achieve target volume in 2023 by providing them with an incentive alignment program.

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